

Ecology of mammalian species in urban and rural landscapes of Gujranwala, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

The number of people living in anthropogenically impacted landscapes is an unexplored and excellent potential to involve the public in ecological study and link them to nature. It is vital to cultivate an admiration for urban flora and wildlife among human populated urban inhabitants in order for cities to be part of maintenance solutions. The purpose of this study was to learn about the diversity of mammals in Gujranwala, Pakistan's urban and rural areas. Data were gathered during the day and night from rural and urban areas in Gujranwala. Species collected from Parks, graveyard, road sides, canals, schools, colleges and rural areas of Gujranwala. Data were collected from January 2019 to December 2022. In the present study we have observed 9 species of mammals. During research noted that 2 species are rare i.e. *Sorex minutus* and *Hystrix indica*, 5 species are common i.e. *Funambulus pennantii*, *Herpestes javanicus*, *Herpestes edwardsii*, *Canis aureus* and *Sus scrofa* and 2 species are abundant as *Rattus rattus* and *Mus musculus*. This is found that area has high diversity of mammalian species.

Keywords: Urban, Mammals, Gujranwala, Species.

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INTRODUCTION

Humans live on an anthropogenic impacted land, and nowhere are this more evident than in the cities of world. More over 10% of the total land of Earth area is currently classified as urban land, and the rate of urbanization continues to be astounding. The bulk of the population already extant in cities, as well as the urban population in global is predicted to reach approximately 5 billion by 2030. The tremendous development of metropolitan areas will surely continue to affect the globe's ecosystem, with far-reaching effects for biodiversity across the world (Altaf *et al.*, 2012a; Seto *et al.*, 2012; Altaf, 2016; Acuto *et al.*, 2018).

Cities, being the world are newest and fastest expanding ecosystems provide a exceptional chance for research, particularly conservation. The amount of people present in anthropogenically impacted landscapes is an unexplored and excellent potential to involve the people in study of ecology and link them to nature. Educating an admiration for flora and wildlife in urban among human city inhabitants is critical

for cities to be part of solutions of conservation. As a means of protecting wildlife and biodiversity, connecting people to nature via thoughtful city development has enormous promise. This strategy, known as "reconciliation ecology," might help conservation of wildlife even in urban areas. Though cities are not normally created with natural animals and plants in mind, they have essential animal habitats, like golf courses, nature preserves, cemeteries, parks, and in rare cases (Dickinson *et al.*, 2012; Belaire *et al.*, 2014; Gallo *et al.*, 2017). This research was planned to know the ecology of mammals in urban and rural areas of Gujranwala, Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data were collected from the rural and urban sites of Gujranwala day and night hours. Data collected from Parks, graveyard, road sides, canals, schools, colleges and “peri-urban areas” of Gujranwala. Research data were collected from January 2019 to December 2022.

STUDY AREA

Gujranwala is the capital of the Gujranwala Division in Pakistan. It is also known as the "City of Wrestlers" and is well-renowned for its cuisine. After Karachi, Lahore, Faisalabad, and Rawalpindi, it is the fifth most populated city in Pakistan (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of Gujranwala.

Gujranwala, which means "Abode of the Gujjars" in Punjabi, was named after the Gujjar clan of northern Punjab. According to one local legend, the town was called after a Gujjar, Choudhry, Gujjar, who owned the Persian wheel that provided water to the town (Figure 1).

Gujranwala's climate is hot and semi-arid, and it fluctuates throughout the year. Summer temperatures range from 36-42 °C from June through September. The coolest months are typically November through February, when temperatures can dip to an average of 7 degrees Celsius. As the monsoon arrives in Punjab, the months with the most precipitation are generally July and August. The average rainfall throughout the other months is roughly 25 millimeters. From October through May, there is minimal rain.

METHODOLOGY

For identification purpose field guides of "Mammals of Pakistan" (Roberts, 2005b, a) were consulted. ArcGIS is used to make map of the study area.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data were analysis through MS excel (2010) and R Statistical software (3.6.3).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study we have observed 9 species of mammals (Table 1). During research noted that 2 species are rare i.e. *Sorex minutus* and *Hystrix indica*, 5 species are common i.e. *Funambulus pennantii*, *Herpestes javanicus*, *Herpestes edwardsii*, *Canis aureus* and *Sus scrofa* and 2 species are abundant as *Rattus rattus* and *Mus musculus* (Figure 2).

Trash in metropolitan areas contains food for mammalian species, which carnivorous and omnivorous animals can devour (Hirasawa *et al.*, 2006). Researchers have reported mammalian species from different cities of Pakistan as Trimmu, Punjab (Ijaz and Adil, 2021), Tharparkar district, Sindh (Khan *et al.*, 2015), Mahaban and Malka Valley District Buner (Akhtar *et al.*, 2018), Harighal, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan (Abbasi, 2021), Gujranwala, Punjab (Altaf *et al.*, 2012b), Dhirkot, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (Riaz and Altaf, 2021), Chenab riverine forest, Punjab (Altaf *et al.*, 2014), Chenab (Altaf, 2016), Bagh, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (Faiz, 2022), and Abbaspur, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan (Rasheed *et al.*, 2020).

The findings show that open environment with animal food is a major role in the dispersion of mammals. Food and anthropogenic shelters, such as roofs and home spaces, are provided by urban and rural places. Certain animal species are naturally shy, and they dislike human interference in their surroundings. This might have a significant role in the dispersion of mammals in urban settings. Yet, they penetrate inhabited areas when humans are not there or at night, such as Asian jackal and wild boar. People, on the other hand, are frequently unaware of the existence of medium or small-sized mammals, despite the fact that these species live near homes.

Figure 2: Status of mammals' in Gujranwala (code are present in table 1).

Table 1: Mammalian species of Gujranwala.

Sr.	Name	Scientific name	Code	Status
1	Mediterranean pygmy shrew	<i>Sorex minutus</i>	MPS	R
2	Northern palm squirrel	<i>Funambulus pennantii</i>	NPS	C
3	House rat	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	HR	A
4	House mouse	<i>Mus musculus</i>	HM	A
5	Small Indian mongoose	<i>Herpestes javanicus</i>	SIM	C
6	Indian grey mongoose	<i>Herpestes edwardsii</i>	IGM	C
7	Golden jackal	<i>Canis aureus</i>	GJ	C
8	Indian wild boar	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	IWB	C
9	Indian crested porcupine	<i>Hystrix indica</i>	JC	R

Note: R (Rare), C (Common), A (Abundant)

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